

Removal of fluoride from drinking water by adsorption on Zr-treated laterite soil using response surface methodology

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Manuscript received 15 November 2017, revised 09 March 2018, accepted 13 March 2018

Abstract : A study on the adsorption of fluoride was conducted using Zr-treated laterite soil as adsorbent. X-Ray Diffraction analysis (XRD) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) were used to characterize the treated laterite soil as adsorbent. Response surface methodology (RSM) was employed to investigate the effect of different operating parameters namely, adsorbent dose, initial concentrations of fluoride and contact time on the uptake of fluoride from aqueous solution. A two level three factor (2^3) central composite design (CCD) was used for determining the optimum experimental conditions and interactions of process variables. The optimum adsorbent dose, initial concentrations of fluoride and contact time were found to be 2.93 g/L, 40 mg/L and 88.5 min respectively. Fluoride removal was 96.32% at the optimum combination of process parameters. This adsorbent can hence be suggested as an appropriate material for the removal of fluoride.

Keywords : Laterite soil, response surface methodology, central composite design, process parameters.

I. Introduction

Intake of fluoride through drinking water is beneficial for the healthy formation and maintenance of teeth and bones especially for growing child. The deficiency of fluoride can cause poor dental health and osteoporosis^{1,2}. However, excessive amount of fluoride causes significant health effects in humans³, which leads to serious dental and skeletal fluorosis⁴. According to the specification of World Health Organization (WHO), the permissible concentration of fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg/L⁵. Therefore, it is more important to develop cost-effective strategies for the removal of excess amount of fluoride from the drinking water to reduce the health risk.

A variety of technologies have been developed, including adsorption, precipitation, electrocoagulation, ion-exchange, electrodialysis and reverse osmosis for defluoridation of water^{1,6-9}. Among these methods, considering cost-effectiveness, ease in operation and flexibility of operation, adsorption tech-

nology is still one of the most extensively used methods. A wide range of adsorbents have been reported for fluoride removal such as alumina-based sorbents¹⁰, iron-based sorbents¹¹, zirconium-based sorbents¹², manganese-based sorbents¹³, zeolite-based sorbents¹⁴, nano-hydroxyapatite¹⁵, biosorbents¹⁶ and chitosan beads¹⁷. Among them, the zirconium loaded-adsorbents have recently received increasing attentions due to their high affinities to fluoride and relatively cost effectiveness.

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a combination of mathematical and statistical techniques used for the optimization of processes and to evaluate the effects of several independent variables¹⁸. The objective of RSM is to investigate the interactive effect of process variables and to determine the optimum operational conditions of process.

Under the study, the combined effect of adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride and contact time on the removal of fluoride from drinking

water by Zr-treated laterite soil has been investigated using central composite design (CCD) in response surface methodology (RSM) by Design Expert Version 10 (Stat Ease, USA).

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

Sodium fluoride (NaF), zirconyl chloride octahydrate ($ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$), HCl and NH_4OH were used in the experiments. All chemicals used, were all of analytical grade (Merck, India).

B. Preparation of sorbent

Red soil was collected from Suri village, Birbhum district, West Bengal, India. The soil was washed three times with de-ionized water to remove the earthy material and dried in a dryer at $80^\circ C$ for 24 h. Then it was ground using a ball mill and sieved with screen of 100 mesh size. The procedure was repeated until powdery soil obtained which was ready to use. Zirconyl chloride octahydrate of 133 mg was dissolved in 25 mL distilled water. The powdery red soil of 5 g was mixed well with the solution. Then 100 ml of 1 (N) HCl was added to the mixture and continuously stirred for 2 h. After that the pH of the solution was maintained at pH 7.5 by adding 1 (N) NH_4OH solutions dropwise under a vigorous stirring condition for 30 min. This led to the formation of precipitate. After filtering the precipitation it was dried at $60^\circ C$ for 24 h and ground manually to fine powder. The dried solid was used as adsorbent in the experiments.

C. Analytical method

In this study, fluoride concentration was measured by SPADNS method¹⁹ using a standard curve, which was prepared by known concentration of NaF. The optical density (OD) or absorbance was measured by UV-Spectrophotometer (HITACHI, India) at 570 nm.

D. Batch studies

Batch experiments have been conducted in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with 100 mL working volume. The flasks were shaken at 200 rpm and main-

tained at $25^\circ C$ for 4 h. At equilibrium, samples were filtered using Whatman filter paper no. 42 and residual fluoride concentration of the filtrate was measured.

E. Response surface methodology for optimisation of adsorption parameters

The influence of different operating parameters namely adsorbent dose (1.5–3.5 g/L), initial concentrations of fluoride (20–40 mg/L) and contact time (30–90 min) on the uptake of fluoride from aqueous solution were conducted in 20 batch runs using RSM. Three factors were studied and their low and high levels are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental range and levels of independent process variables

Variables	Factors	Range and levels (coded)				
		$-\alpha$	-1	0	+1	$+\alpha$
Adsorbent dose (mg/L)	X1	0.82	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.18
Initial conc. of fluoride (mg/L)	X2	13.18	20	30	40	46.81
Contact time (min)	X3	9.54	30	60	90	110.45

Design Expert Version 10 (Stat Ease, USA) was used for the development of mathematical model by regression analysis of the experimental data. Prediction of the optimal point was based upon the quadratic equation model given below (eq. (1)).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=i+1}^k \beta_{ij} x_i x_j + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where, Y = response (i.e. dependent variable), β_0 = constant coefficient, $\beta_i = \beta_{ii} = \beta_{ij}$ = coefficients of linear, quadratic and interaction effect, x_i and x_j = factors (independent variables) and ε = error.

Percent removal of fluoride was calculated with a standard RSM design (CCD) from twenty batch described in Table 2.

Table 2. Central composite design (CCD) for three independent variables used in this study along with the observed response

Experimental run	X1	X2	X3	R (%)
1	2.5	30	110.45	96.31
2	2.5	46.81	60	88.54
3	3.5	20	30	76.72
4	1.5	40	90	90.42
5	2.5	30	9.54	69.25
6	4.18	30	60	92.16
7	3.5	40	30	78.84
8	2.5	30	60	82.32
9	1.5	20	90	84.61
10	2.5	13.18	60	87.83
11	3.5	20	90	96.04
12	0.82	30	60	85.62
13	1.5	20	30	79.48
14	3.5	40	90	92.06
15	2.5	30	60	90.34
16	2.5	30	60	90.96
17	2.5	30	60	90.76
18	1.5	40	30	78.62
19	2.5	30	60	82.92
20	2.5	30	60	82.05

F. Characterization of adsorbent

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) was used to investigate the crystalline structure of adsorbent (figure not shown). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

analysis was also conducted to identify the chemical groups into the adsorbent (figure not shown). The suitability of Zr-treated laterite soil has been analyzed properly to be used as adsorbent.

III. Results and discussion

A. Response surface estimation for maximum removal of fluoride

Batch study was performed to verify the effect of different parameters responsible for fluoride removal. It was observed that adsorbent dose, initial concentrations of fluoride and contact time had higher effect on fluoride removal than other parameters. So, these three parameters were taken for further study.

An empirical relationship between the response (*R*) and the independent variables has been expressed by the following quadratic model.

$$\begin{aligned} \% \text{Removal of fluoride } (R) = & 68.57565 - 2.21206 \times X1 + 0.16962 \times X2 + 0.26845 \times X3 - \\ & 0.087500 \times X1 \times X2 + 0.070833 \times X1 \times X3 + \\ & 4.16667E-004 \times X2 \times X3 + 0.45091 \times X1^2 + \\ & 9.73558E-004 \times X2^2 - 1.85601E-003 \times X3^2 \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

The results of second-order response surface model in the form of analysis of variance (ANOVA) are shown in Table 3. The statistical significance of the model equation was evaluated by the *F*-test ANOVA.

Table 3. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the response surface quadratic model

Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean square	<i>F</i> -Value	<i>P</i> -Value (Probability > <i>F</i>)
Model	808.91	9	89.88	6.36	< 0.0001
A-X1	37.97	1	37.97	2.69	< 0.0001
B-X2	1.60	1	1.60	0.11	< 0.0001
C-X3	680.58	1	680.58	48.17	< 0.0001
AB	6.13	1	6.13	0.43	< 0.0001
AC	36.13	1	36.13	2.56	0.0029
BC	0.13	1	0.13	8.847E-003	< 0.0001
A ²	2.93	1	2.93	0.21	0.0016
B ²	0.14	1	0.14	9.668E-003	< 0.0001
C ²	40.21	1	40.21	2.85	< 0.0001
Residual	141.29	10	14.13		
Lack of fit	45.29	5	9.06	0.47	0.054
Pure error	96.00	5	19.20		
Cor total	950.20	19			

The significance of each coefficient was determined by F -values and P -values. It was observed from Table 3 that the coefficients for the main and square effects were highly significant ($P < 0.0001$) in comparison with interaction effects.

For the regression eq. (2), the R^2 (coefficient of determination) value of 0.964 and adjusted R^2 value of 0.927 suggested a good agreement between the experimental results and their predictions (Table 3). The standard ANOVA (analysis of variance) results calculated from experimental runs are shown in Table 3. The significance of the model equations was confirmed by Fischer's F -test. The value of F was 6.36 for percent removal of fluoride model. The P -value of each model was less than 0.0001, thus the model is statistically significant. The linear, interaction and quadratic coefficient of adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride and contact time were significant. As shown in Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the response surface plots depict the optimum condition for percent removal of fluoride from drinking water. Maximum fluoride removal of 96.32% has been achieved for the optimum values of independent parameters, namely adsorbent dose of 2.93 g/L, initial fluoride concentration of 40 mg/L and contact time of 88.5 min.

Fig. 1. Response surface plots for fluoride removal efficiency (%) : Effect of adsorbent dose (X_1) and initial concentrations of fluoride (X_2).

Fig. 2. Response surface plots for fluoride removal efficiency (%) : Effect of adsorbent dose (X_1) and contact time (X_3).

Fig. 3. Response surface plots for fluoride removal efficiency (%) : Effect of initial concentrations of fluoride (X_2) and contact time (X_3).

B. Optimization using the desirability function

The possible goals for the independent factors and response have been chosen from the design software in numerical optimization. The desired goals were maximize, minimize, target, within range, none (for responses only) and set to an exact value (factors

Fig. 4. Desirability ramp for numerical optimization of four goals, namely adsorbent dose, initial concentrations of fluoride, contact time and percent removal of fluoride.

Fig. 5. Predicted vs actual % removal of fluoride.

only). A minimum and a maximum level must be provided for each parameter. In order to adjust the shape of particular desirability function, a weight can be assigned to each goal. The overall desirability functions are the combination of goals. The range of desirability is started from zero outside of the limits, to one at the goal. It is an objective function. Purpose of the programme is to maximize the function. The goal starts at a random starting point and reaches the steepest slope to a maximum. There are two or more maximums due to the curvature in the response surfaces in the desirability function. The response method was used to optimize any combination of four goals, namely adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride, contact time and percent-

age removal of fluoride. A ramp desirability was obtained from 10 optimum points using numerical optimization as shown in Fig. 4. From 10 optimum points in the response surface modeling, the best values of factors namely adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride and contact time was found to be 2.93 g/L, 40 mg/L, 88.5 min respectively with fluoride removal of 96.32%. The estimated function should fulfill the expectation of experimental model with desired conditions obtained from the data of desirability.

C. Confirmation experiments

Confirmatory experiments were conducted to optimize the data obtained from numerical modeling. Under optimized conditions, the values of three parameters such as adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride and contact time were found to be 2.93 g/L, 40 mg/L, 88.5 min respectively with the fluoride removal of 96.32% as suggested by the model. The deviation was 0.1%. From Fig. 5, it was observed that the deviation of predicted % removal and actual % removal was very less.

IV. Conclusion

The aim of study was to scale-up of the fluoride adsorption process onto Zr-treated laterite soil and to investigate the effect of various process parameters on fluoride removal using response surface methodology. The fluoride removal efficiency was significantly influenced by the adsorbent dose, ini-

tial concentration of fluoride and time of contact. Optimum conditions for the removal of fluoride were obtained by applying a desirability function in RSM. The values of process variable namely adsorbent dose, initial concentration of fluoride and contact time were found to be 2.93 g/L, 40 mg/L and 88.5 min respectively for maximum fluoride removal. The corresponding removal efficiency of fluoride in optimum conditions was found to be 96.32%.

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